

IJCITR

INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF CONTEMPORARY ISSUES AND TRENDS IN RESEARCH

Eleiv Publishing Group, USA

VOLUME 2, ISSUE 1, JANUARY, 2024

ISSN: 3026-9733

Umoh A. Kofi & Nsikak Stephen Edet

China – US Trade War: Implications for the Nigerian Economy

¹Umoh A. Kofi, PhD & ²Nsikak Stephen Edet

^{1&2}Department of Political Science and Public Administration, University of Uyo, Uyo.

¹08063229712; ²08069212110

¹kofiumoh4@gmail.com; ²nsikakstephen@yahoo.com

Abstract

One of the world's major trade wars is underway between the US and China. President Donald Trump imposed 25% tariffs on \$250 billion in Chinese imports by mid-May 2019. He started the administrative process to cover \$300 billion in US imports from China. China retaliated to the trade battle by placing a 25% tariff on \$50 billion in US imports in July and August 2019. The study employed historical and descriptive research methodologies. The study used content analysis and secondary data from library materials like textbooks and journals, online articles, and newspapers and magazines to find and sort significant information. The bulk of the literature review were analysed using the research questions. The researcher relied on content analysis and secondary data. The study's major finding is that exporters' responses to trade war pricing shifts, not specialisation patterns, determine trade conflict winners and losers. The researcher used the Ricardian Theory of Comparative Advantage. This view justifies international trade based on its pros and cons. The study suggests the Nigerian government pursue a flexible and fair bilateral trade policy. This will allow Nigeria to capitalise on the US-China trade war's market gap.

1 Introduction

After Donald Trump's inauguration, the US administration took a trade policy stance before the China-US trade war. Trump started a 'Section 232 review' into Chinese steel and aluminum imports in June 2017, citing national security concerns. Given its steel and aluminum manufacturing capacity, China was seen as the target of extra levies. Trade conflicts between the US and China have grown in scale and frequency in 2018. The US has imposed antidumping levies on Chinese imports all year. Trump ordered an Executive Memorandum to launch a 'Section 301 probe' into China's intellectual property practices in March 2018, escalating trade tensions. He threatened to impose

IJCITR

INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF CONTEMPORARY ISSUES AND TRENDS IN RESEARCH

Eleiv Publishing Group, USA

VOLUME 2, ISSUE 1, JANUARY, 2024

ISSN: 3026-9733

Umoh A. Kofi & Nsikak Stephen Edet

more tariffs on Chinese products. The next day, China issued a similar statement, warning of further taxes on American exports. On April 4, 2018, the US listed 1,333 Chinese products worth \$50 billion that would be subject to a 25% tax. China immediately retaliated by taxing a variety of American goods of equal value, mimicking the US's warnings.

On May 17, Vice Premier Liu He led a Chinese delegation to the US. A joint proclamation was produced after a meeting with US President Donald Trump and extensive negotiations with US trade leaders Steven Mnuchin, Wilbur Ross, and Robert Lighthizer. This declaration shows cooperation and a brief drop in trade tensions. The US Trade Representative (USTR) announced a \$50 billion tariff list on June 16, 2018, including over 1,000 Chinese imports. The Customs Tariff Commission of the State Council in China promptly released a notification, declaring taxes on 659 American items produced domestically with a total value of US\$50 billion. Simultaneously, the Ministry of Commerce announced that prior efforts to negotiate with the United States had been unsuccessful, thereby commencing the China-US trade dispute. As of August 23, 2018, the United States has implemented a 25% tariff on Chinese goods worth \$50 billion, as it had previously threatened to do. In response to the actions taken by the United States, China imposed a supplementary duty of 25% on American goods, amounting to a total value of US\$50 billion.

The trade battle between the United States and China transpired through a sequence of tariff escalations spanning from 2018 to 2019. The Phase One deal, agreed upon by both countries in January 2020, aimed to reduce trade tensions. However, as of late 2021, the tariffs have not been lifted (Bown and Kolb, 2021). In February 2018, after conducting a Section 201 inquiry on solar panels and washing machines, the US International Trade Commission concluded that the importation of these goods had harmed domestic manufacturers. As a result, President Trump implemented protective duties. The initial tariff measures were directed at certain products originating from many countries. Subsequently, the Commerce Department levied further duties on steel and aluminium following Section 232 investigations. These tariffs were specifically aimed at several countries, notably China, while initially exempting certain major economies such as the European Union and Canada. China and other trade partners enacted retaliatory tariffs as a response. After signing the agreement in January 2020,

both sides agreed to reduce September 2019 tariffs by 50%. As of September 2021, tariffs remain.

Given their magnitudes, 17.6% of US imports were tariffed in 2017, including those of international trade partners. Imports made up 15% of GDP in 2016, so the US raised import duties, which accounted for 2.6% of GDP. Average rates rose from 3.7% to 25.8%. Fajgelbaum et al. (2020) reported that trade partners retaliated for 8.7% of shipments in 2017. Exports made up 12% of the 2016 GDP. Thus, trade partners retaliated against exports, which made up 1% of US GDP. This raised average tariffs from 7.7% to 20.8%. US and Chinese tariffs targeted 3.6% of US GDP in imports and exports. China raised taxes on 11% of imports, and the US targeted 18% of exports (Chang et al., 2021). In 2017, the trade war affected 5.5% of China's GDP, with imports accounting for 17.9% and exports for 19.7% (Bown, 2021). China reduced Most Favoured Nation (MFN) tariffs on 10% of its imports, limiting US market access. Nigeria and China started it bilateral trade through it Chambers of Commerce in 1994, and it was not functional until the commencement of the Nigerian fourth Republic 1999 when President Olusegun Obasanjo became the President of Nigeria, coincidentally this was the period the Chinese Government had a new Foreign Policies in Africa in 2000, during the second term of President Obasanjo Government (2003 – 2007), The President of China, Hu Jintao and his Prime Minister Wen Jiabao visited Nigeria, and with that same period the Nigerian Government lead by President Obasanjo and his economic term visited China twice, this was in the bid to leverage on the bilateral and mutual relationship and this lead to the both Countries to develop and intensify their friendship and this lead to the establishment of Nigeria trade office in China in 2001, and in response, Chinese Government established the Chinese Investment Development and trade promotion Centre, by 2006 the intergovernmental Nigeria-China investment forum came into existence (Umo-Udo N.; Orifa J., 2018).

2. Statement of the Problem

Trade disputes between China and the US began in January 2018 when the US imposed duties on major household washing machines, solar cells, and modules, slowing global growth. A broad trade dispute has resulted from these conflicts. Amid promises of more tariffs and retaliation, China and the US, the world's two largest trading nations, grow in

antagonism. If trade tensions between China and the US increase, the IMF (2018) anticipates a 0.9% drop in US GDP and a 0.6% drop in Chinese GDP. This would reduce long-term global GDP by 0.4%. In July 2018, the European Commission lowered its EU economic growth forecast. This shows that trade tensions affect more than China and the US. According to existing patterns, the US-China trade war may become a new Cold War. This will threaten global political and economic stability, including Nigeria's socio-economic and national growth.

Nigeria, with its 923,763 km² of fertile land, might become a major agricultural supplier to China and other Asian nations amid the US-China trade war. Increased taxes on Chinese imports will cause shortages in the U.S. Due to Chinese tariffs, exports from other countries will benefit. This opens new doors for Nigerian exports in the dwindling US market. Carmen Ling, Managing Director and Global Head of RMB Solutions, told Reuters that Kenya and Nigeria will benefit from China's planned rise in African imports. Nigeria is likely to export oil and Kenyan agricultural products. Thus, the Nigerian government must be proactive in creating and executing policies to help it enter global markets (Adesoji, 2019).

Despite the U.S.-China Trade War, Nigeria has commercial links with China and the US. The US is Nigeria's largest foreign investor; however, it invests mostly in petroleum, mining, and wholesale trade. China was Nigeria's largest import partner in the fourth quarter of 2018, with imports estimated at N900 billion, according to the NBS. China's economic slowdown reduces investment flows, leading to capital outflows to safer assets and a drop in developing economy asset values. Currency stability, commercial activity, and investor sentiment are also affected. The trade dispute has hurt demand for iron ore, coal, and platinum. Nigeria, which relies on Chinese commerce, is suffering economically. It has been argued in various quarters regarding China's industrial development that it has serious effects on Nigerian industrial output. (World Development Indicators WDI 2019) sighted in Obikaeze et al. (2023). This study will examine how the US-China trade war affected Nigeria's economy.

3. Objectives of the Study

The primary objective of this study is to analyse the repercussions of the trade battle between China and the United States on the economy of Nigeria.

IJCITR

INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF CONTEMPORARY ISSUES AND TRENDS IN RESEARCH

Eleiv Publishing Group, USA

VOLUME 2, ISSUE 1, JANUARY, 2024

ISSN: 3026-9733

Umoh A. Kofi & Nsikak Stephen Edet

The study has the following specific objectives:

- a. To evaluate the consequences of the trade battle between the United States and China on the global economy.
- b. To examine the effect of the trade battle between the United States and China on Nigeria's commerce.
- c. To assess the implications of the trade battle between the United States and China on Nigeria's socio-economic progress.

4. Research Questions

- a. What are the ramifications of the trade battle between the United States and China on the global economy?
- b. How does the US-China trade disagreement impact Nigeria's trade?
- c. What are the consequences of the trade battle between the United States and China on Nigeria's socio-economic development?

5. Significance of the Study

The study is essential as it will provide a comprehensive understanding of the patterns and progress of the trade dispute between the United States and China and its impact on the Nigeria's economy. It will also create awareness and draw attention to the dangers, consequences and implications of US-China trade conflict on Nigeria's economy, while charting the course of positioning the government to benefit maximally from the conflict instead of suffering from it. Ultimately, this research will not only add to the existing literature on the subject matter, it will also serve as a reference document for further research as well as make vital contributions to related studies in this regard.

6. Review of Related Literature

This section will review what other authors, informants, researchers and analysts wrote about the subject matter of this paper. This will be done under different subheadings:

6.1 Understanding trade conflict

A trade conflict occurs when one nation raises import duties or restricts imports from another. A trade conflict may emerge if a country believes another is trading unfairly. Domestic trade unions or industry lobbyists can influence legislators to limit the appeal

IJCITR

INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF CONTEMPORARY ISSUES AND TRENDS IN RESEARCH

Eleiv Publishing Group, USA

VOLUME 2, ISSUE 1, JANUARY, 2024

ISSN: 3026-9733

Umoh A. Kofi & Nsikak Stephen Edet

of imported goods to consumers, pushing foreign policy towards a trade war. Lack of understanding of the many benefits of unrestrained trade causes trade wars (Chen, Kelly, & Kvilhaug, 2022).

Protectionism often leads to trade wars. Protectionism involves government policies that restrict cross-border trade. Countries typically shield domestic industries and jobs from international competition. Trade deficits are addressed by protectionism. A trade deficit occurs when a country's imports exceed its exports. In the context of a worldwide economy, a trade dispute has the potential to cause significant harm to the consumers and enterprises of both countries. Furthermore, this negative impact might spread and influence various parts of both economies. Typically, it originates in a specific sector and then spreads to impact other areas. Similarly, a trade dispute that originates between two nations might have repercussions on other nations that were not initially part of the trade fight (Chen, Kelly, and Kvilhaug, 2022). A trade conflict is differentiated from other measures implemented to regulate the flow of exports and imports, like sanctions. The trade-related objectives of this initiative have a negative impact on the trading partnership between two nations, causing harmful consequences. Protectionist policies can be enacted through several means, such as imposing import restrictions, establishing stringent product standards, or providing government incentives to discourage outsourcing. These measures, along with tariffs, serve to protect domestic industries. Just like every other social concept, trade conflict has some advantages as well as disadvantages, as follows:

Advantages

- a. Safeguards domestic enterprises against unjust competition.
- b. Enhances the demand for domestic goods.
- c. Stimulates local job creation.
- d. Enhances trade balance.
- e. Penalises nations with unethical trade practices.

Disadvantages

- a. Raises expenses and triggers inflation.
- b. Leads to scarcity in the market and limits options.
- c. Dampens commercial activities.

- d. Impedes economic expansion
- e. Damages diplomatic relations and cultural interchange

Protectionism often hinders market access, economic growth, and cultural exchange, according to critics. Consumers may have fewer market options. They could potentially experience shortages in the absence of a readily available domestic alternative for the imported commodities that have been affected or abolished by tariffs. Manufacturers' profit margins are negatively impacted since they are required to incur additional expenses for raw materials. This phenomenon can result in price escalations, particularly in the realm of manufactured goods, hence instigating inflation within the local economy as a whole (Chen, Kelly, & Kvilhaug, 2022). Example of a trade conflict is that of United States and China which is the main focus of this paper.

6.2 Evolutionary trends in the US-China trade conflict

Mullen (2021) avers that the US-China trade war began in July 2018 under former President Donald Trump. This dispute led to tariffs on US\$185 billion in US goods and US\$550 billion in Chinese imports. Since then, there have been series of talk of wars as seen below:

1. The US-China trade war began on 06/07/2018. The US charges 25% tariffs on \$34 billion in Chinese imports, including cars, hard drives, and aircraft parts. China reacted by imposing a 25% tariff on 545 American agricultural products, cars, and marine products worth US\$34 billion.
2. On September 24, 2018, the US imposed US\$200 billion in taxes on Chinese exports. In response, China acted. The US put a 10% tariff on \$200 billion in Chinese goods. China responded with \$60 billion in tariffs on American goods.
3. On May 31, 2019, China declares its intention to create an "unreliable entity list". The Ministry of Commerce has announced its intention to blacklist foreign enterprises or persons that have contravened market regulations and contractual duties, or have implemented "discriminatory measures" that harm the rights and interests of Chinese businesses, as well as national security and interests (Mullen 2021).

IJCITR

INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF CONTEMPORARY ISSUES AND TRENDS IN RESEARCH

Eleiv Publishing Group, USA

VOLUME 2, ISSUE 1, JANUARY, 2024

ISSN: 3026-9733

Umoh A. Kofi & Nsikak Stephen Edet

4. On January 6, 2019, China raised tariffs on US\$60 billion worth of American goods. The Ministry of Finance has announced that the increase in duties to "25, 20, and 10 percent" is a direct response to the issues of unilateralism and trade protectionism.
5. On June 29, 2019, Xi and Trump once again reached an agreement to temporarily halt the trade dispute during the G20 conference in Japan. Donald Trump expressed that the result was "more favourable than anticipated", as China stated that the US has agreed to refrain from imposing additional tariffs on its products.
6. On May 8, 2019, the United States officially classified China as a 'currency manipulator' due to the decline of the yuan below the significant level of 7 against the US dollar. This level had been previously defended by the People's Bank of China (PBOC). It was the initial occurrence of it dropping below the significant psychological threshold since 2008.
7. On August 13, 2019, the United States announced that certain proposed tariffs have been either postponed or eliminated. Donald Trump declared that the proposed tariffs on a significant portion of Chinese goods worth US\$300 billion, which were scheduled to begin in September 2019, have either been postponed or eliminated. However, 10% duties on US\$155 billion in goods such as phones, laptops, and video gaming consoles would be deferred until December 15.
8. On November 10, 2019, President Trump announced that a significant "phase-one deal" has been made and that the implementation of new tariffs will be postponed. He announced that his negotiators have achieved a significant phase-one agreement, which will postpone the imposition of additional US tariffs on Chinese imports. This outcome follows two days of intensive trade negotiations between the two countries, with the objective of making progress towards resolving their contentious bilateral trade dispute.
9. On 14/02/2020, China reduced additional tariffs on American items, amounting to US\$75 billion that were imposed in 2019. These products include automotive and

agricultural goods such as pigs, chicken, cattle, and soybeans, as well as chemicals, crude oil, whisky, and seafood. China has rescinded its prohibition on importing live poultry products from the United States.

10. On February 18, 2021, US Treasury Secretary, Yellen affirmed that the tariffs imposed on China will be maintained. "Currently, we have maintained the tariffs implemented by the Trump administration. Moving forward, we will assess what we deem suitable," states US Treasury Secretary, Janet Yellen in an interview with CNBC. She further emphasised that the United States anticipates Beijing to uphold its trade obligations (Mullen 2021).
11. On May 27, 2021, Liu He and Katherine Tai engaged in the initial trade negotiations that started in August 2020. Chinese Vice-Premier, Liu He and US commerce Representative, Katherine Tai engaged in a telephone conversation, during which Beijing emphasised the significance of fostering bilateral commerce following a "frank and constructive" discussion.
12. On 15/07/2021, US Treasury Secretary, Janet Yellen lacked intention to reinstate the US-China Strategic and Economic Dialogue (S&ED) mechanism.
13. On 19/07/2021, US Treasury Secretary, Janet Yellen expressed her belief that the trade pact failed to tackle the underlying issues, stating that the imposition of tariffs on China lacked careful consideration, according to an interview with The New York Times (Mullen 2021).

6.3 Consequences of US-China trade conflict on the global economy

US-China trade tensions have significant effects on the global economy at the consumer level, producer level, and at a macroeconomic level.

At the consumer level

Due to tariffs, US-China trade has decreased, thereby hurting consumers and manufacturers. Other countries with the US and China are also affected by the bilateral

IJCITR

INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF CONTEMPORARY ISSUES AND TRENDS IN RESEARCH

Eleiv Publishing Group, USA

VOLUME 2, ISSUE 1, JANUARY, 2024

ISSN: 3026-9733

Umoh A. Kofi & Nsikak Stephen Edet

trade deficit. Although the impact on global economic development is small, the recent escalation hurts businesses and financial market confidence, disrupts global supply chains, and threatens the 2019 global growth prediction. Consumers worldwide, including in the US and China, have suffered from the trade war. Research by Cavallo, Gopinath, Neiman, and Tang using Bureau of Labour Statistics price data on Chinese imports found that US importers have borne the brunt of tariff revenue (Cerutti, Gopinath, & Mohommad, 2019).

At the producers' level

The impact in this case is somewhat varied, with a few beneficiaries and numerous individuals experiencing negative outcomes. Potential beneficiaries include American and Chinese manufacturers that compete with imported goods subject to tariffs in their respective local markets, as well as exporters from other countries who compete in the global economy. Conversely, both American and Chinese manufacturers of goods impacted by the tariffs, as well as manufacturers who rely on those commodities as intermediate materials, have the potential to have negative consequences.

Trade diversion affects producers. The combined bilateral data from the US suggests a trade diversion, as imports from China decreased while imports from other nations increased. For instance, US imports of taxed Mexican goods increased. China imports dropped \$850 million after the \$16 billion tariff list was implemented in August. This decline was offset by an \$850 million gain in Mexican imports, keeping US imports constant. In Japan, Korea, and Canada, US import growth is lower than in September–November 2017. Aggregate data may mask stockpile use and other factors that affect bilateral trade patterns. Cerutti, Gopinath, and Mohommad (2019) found little change in third-country photosensitive semiconductor device imports. (Cerutti, Gopinath, and Mohommad, 2019).

At the macroeconomic level

This case has some beneficiaries and many losers. Potential benefactors include American and Chinese producers that compete with tariffed imports in their domestic markets and exporters from other countries in the global economy. Conversely, American and Chinese makers of tariff-affected goods and those that use those commodities as intermediary materials may suffer. Trade diversion affects producers. (Cerutti, Gopinath, and Mohommad, 2019).

6.4 Effects of the US-China Trade Conflict on Nigeria's Trade

Nigeria's trading operations are affected by the US-China trade war. There are three primary points of impact:

- a. The effects of Nigeria's trade on the global economy: The trade conflict between China and the United States, being the two largest economies in the world, can be considered a battle between two global economic powerhouses. Consequently, this conflict would have a detrimental impact on the global economy. There exists a correlation between the pace of international trade and worldwide economic expansion. When trade experiences a deceleration, it will have an adverse effect on global economic growth. As a consequence, other significant economic factors will be impacted. Hence, decelerations in the worldwide economy led to reduced demand for commodities, potentially affecting the price of oil, foreign exchange profits, and foreign reserves. Nigeria's oil, agricultural commodities, and other products have experienced losses rather than gains during this period of trade strife (Adesoji, 2019).
- b. The imposition of tariffs on Chinese imports by the United States will result in a shortage of supplies in the US market, affecting Nigeria's trade and export economies. The rising costs of Chinese imports will lead to increased competitiveness of imports from other regions in the US market compared to imports from China. Exports from nations unaffected by the increase in US tariffs will consequently gain a competitive advantage in the United States. In the context of the African Growth and Opportunities Act, this circumstance offers fresh prospects for Nigerian exports in the United States market. As a nation, we still need to cultivate the ability to fully use this potential.
- c. Effects pertaining to Nigeria's Foreign Direct Investments (FDIs): The prevailing situation is likely to induce a shift of investment from China to nations unaffected by the increase in US import tariffs. China currently serves as a prominent centre for exporting goods to the United States of America. Due to the ongoing trade battle, numerous investors in China, whose primary export market is the United States, may now start exploring alternative destinations for their investments. This presents novel prospects for these governments to provide alternate locations

for such investors. Nevertheless, our capacity to capitalise on this opportunity is contingent upon the calibre of our investment climate (Adesoji, 2019).

Implications of US-China trade conflict on Nigeria's socio-economic development

Nigeria possessed a highly varied economy that was driven by the development of wide trade networks connecting various cities and states. Significantly, the majority of these routes were terrestrial, following the course of rivers, while others emerged around maritime hubs, prosperous urban centres that thrived as a result of extensive trade networks.

The country achieved a level of self-sufficiency by relying on its agricultural endeavours. Regrettably, colonial powers established fresh economic sectors to satisfy the material desires of the Western world and primarily interconnected the coastal regions with the Atlantic economy. According to most socio-political economists, this specific action is considered one of the primary causes that have hindered the country's capacity for self-development, despite having been independent for many years (Adesoji, 2019). Although Nigeria is perceived as having the largest economy in Africa based on nominal GDP, its economic growth has been deemed sluggish. This can be attributed to factors such as persistent warfare and unrest, despotic regimes, rampant corruption, international trade policies, and excessive reliance on foreign loans. However, there have been some recent signs of positive progress. As a result of being classified as an impoverished nation, Nigeria mostly exports raw resources and intermediate commodities, which has hindered the country's economic progress. Regrettably, the nation is significantly dependent on foreign assistance for its survival (Adesoji, 2019). The existence of the US-China trade crisis has significant implications for Nigeria's socio-economic growth.

Significantly, Nigeria's trade is primarily influenced by a wide range of abundant natural resources, particularly in the oil industry. The trade battle between the United States and China is causing a decline in the oil market. Additionally, over 70% of exported goods are mostly in their raw form, and trade is heavily reliant on international commerce (Kohnert, 2018). The socio-economic operations in Nigeria carried out by the US and China are considered to be among the most significant compared to other partners like the EU, but the involvement of the US has decreased over time. China has recently emerged as the leading and largest trading partner in the country. Chinese

IJCITR

INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF CONTEMPORARY ISSUES AND TRENDS IN RESEARCH

Eleiv Publishing Group, USA

VOLUME 2, ISSUE 1, JANUARY, 2024

ISSN: 3026-9733

Umoh A. Kofi & Nsikak Stephen Edet

companies have been highly involved in constructing ports, roads, and trains that will support the integration and trade between Nigeria and other African countries. This commitment was recently demonstrated across the continent through the significant African Continental Free Trade Agreement (AfCFTA).

Nigeria has established enduring diplomatic ties with both the United States and China in recent years, resulting in the US-China trade conflict being a significant concern for the country's socio-economic and commercial progress. Nigeria faces the risk of being very susceptible to any potential flaws in the US and Chinese economies due to its tight economic ties with these countries, who are Africa's largest trading partners and key investors. In 2019, when Nigerians expressed strong disapproval of the \$5 billion loan from China, the Debt Management Office (DMO) issued the following statement:

Borrowing from China Exim is one of the means of ensuring that Nigeria has access to more long-term concessional loans. Given the country's infrastructure deficit, which needs to be urgently addressed, the loans from China Exim, which provide financing for critical infrastructure in road and rail transport, aviation, water, agriculture, and power at concessional terms, are appropriate for Nigeria's financing needs and align properly with the country's Debt Management Strategy (Thisday, 2023).

The aforementioned comment suggests that the US-China trade conflict is expected to have a significant and immediate effect on emerging markets, particularly financial markets. This is likely to result in a substantial outflow of money towards safer investments and a decline in the value of risky assets in Nigeria's emerging markets. The International Monetary Fund (2020) has forecast that the country's economic development will be slower than originally anticipated over around two-thirds of the period, although per capita income is expected to climb at a quicker pace. Hence, the outcome heavily relies on the government's reaction and efficient trade strategies that can capitalise on the trade dispute between the United States and China. In contrast, it is anticipated that there will be a gradual increase in growth in industries that require a large number of resources, specifically 2.5 percent (Adesoji, 2019).

7. Theoretical Framework

This research adopts the Ricardian Theory of Comparative Advantage and the Heckscher-Ohlin model. This is because both theories offer some of the most compelling reasons for supporting international trade on a balanced scale.

8. Ricardian Theory of Comparative Advantage

British economist David Ricardo (1772-1823) developed the notion in the early nineteenth century. This approach is based on economic endowments like labour productivity in different nations (Ruffin, 2002). The idea is that a country should produce goods and services at a lower opportunity cost, or autarky pricing, and then trade with another. The idea states that economic resource differences provide countries with a comparative advantage. Comparative advantage is a country's ability to manufacture a good at a lower opportunity cost than others. The theory or model of international commerce is prominent in economic literature because it explains the importance of trade and trade liberalisation for all nations (Rautala, 2015). It makes sense that trade liberalisation policies that highlight a country's natural riches and technological advances will boost domestic economies. Because trade lowers relative marginal costs, they can produce things cheaper (Ruffin, 2002).

Key assumptions underlying Ricardo's theory of comparative advantage include:

1. The production process encompasses solely two categories of items and two nations.
2. The absence of transportation costs can nullify the impact of opportunity cost and influence the selling price.
3. Both countries have two markets that function under conditions of complete competition.
4. The production factor is exclusively comprised of labour.
5. Labour is capable of moving within the home market, but is unable to move between countries.
6. There are only two countries, referred to as A and B.

IJCITR

INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF CONTEMPORARY ISSUES AND TRENDS IN RESEARCH

Eleiv Publishing Group, USA

VOLUME 2, ISSUE 1, JANUARY, 2024

ISSN: 3026-9733

Umoh A. Kofi & Nsikak Stephen Edet

8.1 Research method

The study employed both Historical and Descriptive research methodologies. The rationale behind using this approach is rooted in the fact that the historical/descriptive method provides a more lucid understanding of the US-China trade issues and its influence on Nigeria's economy.

8.2 Method of data collection

The study used library resources such as textbooks, journals, web articles, newspapers, and magazines to gather and categorise relevant data using content analysis and secondary data.

8.3 Method of Data Analysis

Due to the fact that the study relied on content analysis and secondary data to analyse the subject matter of the research, data obtained from the bulk of literature review were analysed using the research questions developed for this study.

9. Data Presentation and Discussion Findings

Discussion under this section will be based on the research questions developed.

Research Question 1

What are the consequences of US-China trade conflict on the global economy?

The long-term goal of decreasing global trade barriers was undermined by China and the US raising tariffs on \$450 billion in products in 2018 and 2019. These tariffs reduced US-China commerce. Global commerce outside these two countries is poorly understood.

"The US-China Trade Conflict and Global Reallocations" (NBER Working Paper 29562) by Pablo Fajgelbaum, Pinelopi K. Goldberg, Patrick J. Kennedy, Amit Khandelwal, and Daria Taglioni found that the US-China trade war improved trade prospects for other nations and increased global trade by 3%. Export growth was stronger in countries with more robust trade agreements and foreign direct investment.

Other nations increased exports to the US and the rest of the world as the US and China put taxes on each other and curtailed trade, strengthening global commerce.

IJCITR

INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF CONTEMPORARY ISSUES AND TRENDS IN RESEARCH

Eleiv Publishing Group, USA

VOLUME 2, ISSUE 1, JANUARY, 2024

ISSN: 3026-9733

Umoh A. Kofi & Nsikak Stephen Edet

US tariffs on Chinese imports increased in 2018 and 2019. It also raised tariffs on goods imported from other countries, mostly equipment and metals. China imposed tariffs on US imports. It decreased import duties from other countries. Compared to worldwide tariff liberalisation, the tariff increases were considerable.

The researchers compared these four groups of tariff modifications with global bilateral trade statistics from the International Commerce Centre for the top 50 exporting countries, excluding oil-exporting nations, to assess their impact on global commerce. They studied the export growth of commodities subject to US or Chinese tariff rises.

The United States and China reduced exports of high-taxed products. Despite a 2.2 percent increase in exports to other countries, US exports to China fell 26.3 percent. China's US exports fell 8.5 percent, but its global exports rose 5.5 percent. The study found that nations not directly involved in the taxes increased commerce in the products affected by the levies. In addition to redirecting global trade patterns, these nations increased their exports. According to estimates, the global response to the trade conflict increased global trade by 3%. Exports to the US and other countries fell due to South African and Philippine tariff increases. Due to tariffs, 19 of the 48 countries' bystander exports increased statistically. The remaining 28 countries had no statistically significant effects, whereas one country declined significantly. Linda Gorman, 2018.

Research Question 2

To what extent does the US-China trade conflict affect Nigeria's trade?

The growing trade disputes between the U.S. and China have kept global markets attentive as concerns permeate the global economy and affect other nations.

Analysts expect trade disagreements between the world's two largest economies to damage economic relations in many countries.

China supplied the majority of U.S. imports in 2017, at over \$500 billion. US exports to China were 185 billion dollars during the same period.

In early 2018, President Donald Trump imposed various tariffs on Chinese goods. China responded with tariffs on American goods.

Subsequently, both nations have reciprocated with retaliatory actions, causing varying degrees of disruption in the global markets. This situation is progressively evolving into a complete trade conflict.

Political economists are concerned that African countries may be adversely affected due to the interconnectedness of global economies. Any economic disturbances in the United States and China can have repercussions on the entire global economy.

According to reports, Nigeria, Kenya, and South Africa's financial markets were hit hard, especially Africa's two largest economies.

According to Mr. Lawrence Freeman, a political-economist analyst located in the United States specialising in Africa, the emerging trade dispute between the two global heavyweights might potentially result in severe economic repercussions for Nigeria.

Freeman expressed concern that if President Trump initiates a comprehensive trade war, it might have severe repercussions for the global economy, impose financial sanctions on China, and weaken China's yuan.

"This has the potential to have detrimental consequences for Nigeria, as both countries are collaborating on currency transfers and have jointly invested billions of dollars to enhance Nigeria's agriculture."

Research Question 3

What are the implications of the US-China trade conflict on Nigeria's socio-economic development?

The US-China trade war threatens Nigeria's economy more than it helps. FEMI ASU wrote it. Nigeria, Africa's top oil producer, is vulnerable to the US-China trade war. Both nations tax each other's imports.

After years of conflict, both nations declared a ceasefire and began discussions in December. Negotiations to resolve the US-China trade war stalled last week.

Last Friday, the United States implemented new tariffs on imports from China.

IJCITR

INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF CONTEMPORARY ISSUES AND TRENDS IN RESEARCH

Eleiv Publishing Group, USA

VOLUME 2, ISSUE 1, JANUARY, 2024

ISSN: 3026-9733

Umoh A. Kofi & Nsikak Stephen Edet

The Trump administration increased taxes from 10 percent to 25 percent on Chinese goods valued at approximately \$200 billion annually.

On Monday, the trade battle intensified significantly when China retaliated by imposing tariffs of 5% to 10% on an additional \$60 billion worth of American goods. This action resulted in the largest decline in US stock prices since January.

In its October assessment of the global economy, the International Monetary Fund cautioned that the trade battle had the potential to worsen the world's economic condition and increase its vulnerability. The organisation stated that a complete trade conflict between the two countries would significantly impede economic recovery.

According to the Financial Times, there has been a significant deceleration in global trade growth since the escalation of the US-China trade dispute in mid-2018. Various economic indicators indicate that this year-long conflict is increasingly impacting the global economy.

"The United States and China are the two largest economies globally. When they have conflicts, their intentions and actions result in a decrease in global economic growth, which will impact the majority of countries." Given our reliance on imports and our primary export of oil, Nigeria will also be impacted.

M. Ekpo, the Professor of Economics and Public Policy at the University of Uyo, emphasised the necessity of diversifying the Nigerian economy to include the exportation of commodities other than crude oil. He stated that if China loses trade with the US, it will seek to compensate by increasing trade with African countries, particularly for consumer items. This is when Nigeria will be impacted. Consequently, they might opt to transport those commodities to Nigeria, but they would be of significantly worse quality. It is imperative that we exercise utmost vigilance and guarantee that the imported items from China to Nigeria meet stringent quality standards. Indeed, we are currently not engaged in such activities.

Conclusion and Recommendations

This empirical study suggests that the US-China trade conflict will not solely result in a detrimental economic impact on the Nigerian economy. In addition to impacting economic growth, both the United States and China, as well as other trading partners worldwide, have major negative consequences.

IJCITR

INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF CONTEMPORARY ISSUES AND TRENDS IN RESEARCH

Eleiv Publishing Group, USA

VOLUME 2, ISSUE 1, JANUARY, 2024

ISSN: 3026-9733

Umoh A. Kofi & Nsikak Stephen Edet

The ever-changing hi-tech industry is causing global communication to speed up. This greatly facilitates the process of international engagement between countries. The utilisation of unjust tariff structures by the US and China as a strategy to disrupt the international system and counteract perceived unfair trade practices has resulted in the emergence of diverse global trade dynamics. While there may be some truth to this statement, it is important to acknowledge that tariff wars can have severe consequences for the participating countries. There is a lack of concrete assumptions regarding the potential effects of a trade conflict on non-participating countries, such as Nigeria. Prominent decision-makers can capitalise on the potential shift of commercial activities to Nigeria by ramping up production to satisfy the substantial demand for exports.

This research recommends the following:

1. The Nigerian government should prioritise the development of flexible and equitable bilateral trade policies to capitalise on the market gap resulting from the trade battle between the United States and China.
2. Furthermore, China's imposition of high tariffs on US technological exports offers a significant opportunity for the country to expand its presence in the global market and address its technology industry's deficit, thereby enhancing its trade deficit.
3. Furthermore, China's implementation of retaliatory tariffs against US farmers who export to the country might be viewed as a potential opportunity to enhance Nigeria's agricultural industry, which significantly contributes to the nation's socio-economic progress. It is important to emphasise that these actions must be carried out in accordance with anti-dumping legislation or regulations.

References

Adesoji, B. S. (2019). US-China Trade conflict: Implications for Nigeria as its Asian romance lingers. Retrieved from <https://nairametrics.com/2019/03/26/us-china-trade-war-implications-for-nigerian-as-its-asian-romance-lingers/> (Accessed on 14th September, 2023).

IJCITR

INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF CONTEMPORARY ISSUES AND TRENDS IN RESEARCH

Eleiv Publishing Group, USA

VOLUME 2, ISSUE 1, JANUARY, 2024

ISSN: 3026-9733

Umoh A. Kofi & Nsikak Stephen Edet

Andrew Mullen (2021). US-China trade conflict timeline: key dates and events since July 2018. Retrieved from https://www.scmp.com/economy/china-economy/article/3146489/us-china-trade-war-timeline-key-dates-and-events-july2018?campaign=3146489&module=perpetual_scroll_0&pgtype=article (Accessed on 10th September, 2023).

Bown CP, Kolb M. (2021). Trump's trade war time line: an up-to-date guide. Peterson Institute for International Economics, Washington DC. <https://www.piie.com/sites/default/files/documents/trump-tradewar-timeline.pdf>. Accessed 20 Oct 2021

Cerutti, E., Gopinath, G. and Mohommad, A. (2019). The Impact of US-China Trade Tensions. Retrieved from <https://www.imf.org/en/Blogs/Articles/2019/05/23/blog-the-impact-of-us-china-trade-tensions> (Accessed on 25th September, 2023).

Chad P. Bown, (2021). "The USA-China trade war and phase one agreement," Working Paper Series WP21-2, Peterson Institute for International Economics.

Chen, J., Kelly, R. and Kvilhaug (2022). Trade conflicts: History, Pros & Cons, and U.S. - China Example. Retrieved from <https://www.investopedia.com/terms/t/trade-war.asp> (Accessed on 14th September, 2023).

Fajgelbaum, P. D., P. K. Goldberg, P. J. Kennedy, and A. K. Khandelwal (2020). The return to protectionism. *The Quarterly Journal of Economics* 135(1), 1–55.

Fajgelbaum, P. and A. K. Khandelwal (2021). The economic impacts of the us-china trade war. *Annual Review of Economics*, Forthcoming.

IJCITR

INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF CONTEMPORARY ISSUES AND TRENDS IN RESEARCH

Eleiv Publishing Group, USA

VOLUME 2, ISSUE 1, JANUARY, 2024

ISSN: 3026-9733

Umoh A. Kofi & Nsikak Stephen Edet

Journal Article | Research Support, Non-U.S. Gov't Authors Chang Y, Lim G, Huh WK
Primary Lit For TOR1 | SSD1 | SCD6 | WHI3

Nasrudin, J. (1996). Globalization and History. *The Journal of Economic History*, 56(02), pp.277-306.

Obikaeze, C.V., Umo-Udo, N.S., Nwokeye., A.N. and Daramola, T.O.(2023). “Nigeria – China Bilateral Relations. Re-Examining the trajectory of the Nigerian Manufacturing Sector” *Journal of Contemporary International Relations and Diplomacy*. Vol.4. No.1.

Rautala, V. (2015). Estimating the Elasticity of Distance with Finnish international Trade flows:
Retrieved from <https://www.thisdaylive.com/index.php/2018/09/16/mudayusuf-us-china-trade-war-has-numerous-implications-on-nigerias-economy> (Accessed on 25th September, 2023).

Ruffin, R. J. (2002). David Ricardo's Discovery of Comparative Advantage. *History of Political Economy*. Retrieved from [http://uh.edu/~rruffin/ricardo's discovery.pdf](http://uh.edu/~rruffin/ricardo's%20discovery.pdf) (Accessed on 17th September, 2023).

Thisday (2023). Muda Yusuf: US-China Trade conflict Has Numerous Implications on Nigeria's Economy using Gravity Model. Retrieved from https://erepo.uef.fi/bitstream/handle/123456789/14925/urn_nbn_fi_uef-20150356.pdf(Accessed on 14th September, 2023).

Umo-Udo, N.S. and Orifa, J.A. (2018) “Nigerian Trade Relations with China: An Assessment (1999 – 2016)” *international Journal of Social and Management Research*. Vol. 4, N09.